

Implications of Radiological Parameters in Round Window Approach in Cochlear Implantation

Safa Abdussalam N K¹, Sunil Kumar K P², Swathilal S A³

¹Senior Resident, Department of ENT, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, Kerala.

²Professor, Department of ENT, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, Kerala.

³Associate Professor, Department of ENT, Government Medical College, Kozhikode, Kerala.

Received: 06-03-2023 / Revised: 30-03-2023 / Accepted: 30-04-2023

Corresponding author: Dr. Safa Abdussalam N.K

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract

Background: Cochlear implantation (CI) has revolutionized the treatment of severe to profound SNHL. Promontory cochleostomy and RW insertion are two common methods for implanting the intracochlear electrode, of which RW insertion is the preferred one due to its atraumatic character. Residual hearing can be preserved by this means. But the major setback is uncertainty regarding RW accessibility prior to surgery and consequently the need to shift the surgical approach. Only way to tackle this is to make use of available imaging modalities to derive maximum information possible prior to surgery, including cochlear orientation, RW accessibility, and major anatomical landmarks, thus guiding surgeon's approach to CI.

Aim and Objectives: (1) To find out the probability of round window rotation by looking into various radiological parameters (2) To compare the findings of preoperative radiological assessment with those obtained during surgery (3) To measure the surgical outcome using intra operative NRT assessment and comparing it with aided audiogram at 3 months and 6 months postoperatively (4) To find out whether early identification of hearing loss, use of hearing aid or early surgery, longer cochlear duct and thicker cochlear nerve will affect hearing outcome (5) To know if congenital / acquired abnormalities in inner ear and incomplete electrode insertion result in poor outcome.

Methods: It was a prospective cohort study done in the department of ENT, GMC Kozhikode on the Cochlear Implant candidates under Sruthitharangam Program from 1st January 2019 to 31st May 2021 with minimum follow up period of 6 months. Data was entered in MS Excel and analyzed using SPSS 20.

Results: Our study included subjects within the age group of 1 to 5 years- 57.5% at 3 years, 27.5% below 3 years and 15% above 3yrs. 70% of study population were males and 30% females. According to our study, the outcome of cochlear implant surgery had no significant relation with age at which the hearing loss was identified, use of hearing aid, age at which surgery was performed, thickness of Cochlear nerve and length of cochlear duct. HRCT was more than 90% accurate in predicting the anatomic landmarks like mastoid cellularity, Korners septum, position of Jugular bulb, sinus plate and Tegmen plate. All 12 cases with RW rotation were accurately predicted from HRCT findings like orientation of cochlear basal turn, angle between lines drawn along the anterior margin of internal auditory canals and plane of incudo-malleal joint and cochlear basal turn. Significant positive correlation was obtained between the thickness of facial nerve and cochlear nerve in IAC. Comparison of aided audiogram at 3 months and 6 months after

surgery showed significant improvement in hearing outcome. Mean hearing level changed from the preoperative value of 77dB to 43 dB at 3 months and 38dB at 6 months.

Conclusion: Preoperative radiological evaluation has great implications in round window approach in cochlear implantation. Having an overview of anatomical landmarks and round window accessibility before surgery will guide the surgeon towards proper surgical approach.

Keywords: Cochlear Implantation; Round Window Approach; Radiology; Audiogram.

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Introduction

Cochlear implantation is one of the most dramatic and life changing medical innovations of the 20th century. A cochlear implant is an implantable prosthesis that electrically stimulates the spiral ganglion cells of cochlear nerve directly in circumstances when the cochlear hair cells themselves do not function effectively. The surgery involves insertion of electrode within the scala tympani of the cochlea where it sits close to the neural elements [1]. Round window approach and promontory cochleostomy approach are the two most common approaches used for electrode insertion [2]. Disruption of the basilar membrane by traumatic insertion or displacement into the scala vestibuli causes complete loss of residual hearing. With the recent increase in interest to minimize surgical trauma and to preserve residual hearing, the importance of approach to scala tympani has increased, and much attention has to be paid in making the opening in the optimum position so as to minimize the intra cochlear damage and insertion related trauma to electrode as well [1]. The promontory cochleostomy approach makes an opening in the basal turn of cochlea located anteroinferiorly to the round window [3]. This method was widely used for several decades as the standard method for cochlear implantation surgery. But this approach can lead to acoustic trauma to the inner ear by transmitting the drill vibration energy since prolonged drilling is required to make an opening that does not exist naturally. On the

other hand, round window approach involves drilling the round window niche to get access to scala tympani [1]. The cochlear implant is an electronic device which is implanted under the skin with electrodes positioned in the cochlea to stimulate the auditory nerve. Electrical currents induce action potentials in the auditory nerve fibers and these are transmitted to the brain. It thus bypasses the damaged or missing hair cells in the cochlea that would normally code sound. It consists of 1. An external part: consisting of the microphone, sound processor, and a transmitter coil. 2. The internal receiver-stimulator, which receives power and decodes instructions for controlling the electrical stimulation. 3. The intracochlear electrode array, which has electrodes placed near the auditory nerve to stimulate the auditory nerve fibers. 4. The external component (speech processor) that contains a microphone picks up and processes the incoming sound to create a set of stimuli for the electrodes. The processed signal, which contains temporal spatial patterns of stimulation, is transmitted to the implanted receiver that decodes the signal and controls an electrical current on each electrode. While these components are common to all the existing systems, the methods of processing the sounds, transmitting the information to the implant and stimulating the electrodes vary from system to system. Also, there are many different electrodes having different shapes and are designed to be placed within the scala tympani. The electrode in CI needs

to be closer to a greater number of auditory nerves to better reproduce more advanced speech processing strategies, in particular stimulations of the physiology [1]. This requires a finer temporal-spatial pattern of activity. The electrodes may lie in scala tympani but directed with control of bending to lie favourably under the spiral lamina. The medical, audiologic, and educational management of children with severe to profound hearing loss has been dramatically altered by the introduction of cochlear implants [4]. Children born with severe to profound deafness are now provided with technological options that can afford them better access to speech and language through audition [5]. As implant technology has matured, the demands of time and money on health care systems has become greater [6]. Although the impact of cochlear implant technology on the education of children with severe to profound hearing loss is still evolving, studies point to successful integration of implant recipient into mainstream at younger ages, pointing to the importance of early identification of hearing loss and timely intervention[7]. As this generation of children with implants passes through the educational system, the outcomes of cochlear implantation appear promising [8]. The parameters are likely to be affected by variations in the origin and course of implantation. Prior knowledge of these variations is important, to avoid complications. In view of CI surgeries being routinely performed now, it is the need of the hour to develop data for each racial group, so that decision regarding ideal surgical approach and electrode designing can be undertaken. With these goals in mind, we have compared our findings with the existing literature.

Aim

To find out the implications of radiological parameters in round window approach of cochlear implantation.

Primary Objective:

To find out the probability of round window rotation by looking into the various radiological parameters.

Secondary Objectives: 1. To compare the findings of preoperative radiological assessment with those obtained during surgery. 2. To measure the surgical outcome using intraoperatively NRT assessment. 3. To measure the outcome of cochlear implantation using aided audiogram at 3 months and 6 months postoperatively. 4. To find out whether cochlear nerve thickness and length of cochlear duct will affect the hearing outcome. 5. To find out whether early surgery results in better hearing outcome. 6. To find out whether early detection of hearing loss and use of hearingaid contribute to better hearing outcome after surgery. 7. To know if the congenital and acquired abnormalities in the inner ear result in poor outcome after surgery. 8. To know if the incomplete electrode insertion can lead to a poor outcome after implantation. 9. To find out if postoperative complications can result in poor hearing outcome.

Candidacy

The Candidacy differs according to the healthcare systems and funding arrangements of different countries. According to the current FDA criteria, indications for cochlear implantation are bilateral profound sensorineural hearing loss for children aged 12-24 months and severe to profound hearing loss for 2-17 years, along with limited benefit from amplification, including minimal or no progress on age-appropriate auditory stimulation [3].

According to the NICE guidelines [9], the criteria for implant include: 1. Any person with severe to profound hearing loss who does not get adequate benefit from acoustic hearing aids. 2. Severe to profound deafness is defined as the ability to hear sounds only

above 90 dB HL at 2 kHz and 4 kHz without hearing aids. 3. Hearing aids should be used for at least 3 months unless inappropriate or contraindicated. 4. Adequate benefit with hearing aids is defined as, for adults:- a score of 50% or greater on Bamford-Kowal-Bench Sentence testing at a sound level of 70 dB spl. 5. For children:- speech, language and listening skills appropriate to the age, developmental stage and the cognitive ability. 6. Assessment should be done by a multidisciplinary team and the tests should be adapted to take into account the candidate's disability as well as their language and communication ability. 7. Simultaneous bilateral CI is recommended for children [15] and for adults who are blind or who have other disabilities that increase their reliance on auditory stimuli as a primary sensory mechanism for spatial awareness [10]. The audiological assessment of potential cochlear implant recipients usually also includes an auditory brainstem response test. This aids in validating the accuracy of the behavioral responses, detecting a central problem or an absent cochlear nerve, and (in older patients) ruling out non-organic hearing loss. [9] It is on taking all this into account that the Kerala Social Security Mission has laid the eligibility criteria, as shown below [11]. The child should be in the age group of 0-3 years. However the Screening Committee would be empowered to make exceptions beyond 3 years, up to 5 years of age on a case to case basis; where the committee feels that a high possibility of success exists, or if there are other compelling technical reasons warranting or making an exception: 1. The annual family income of the applicant should be below Rs. 2 Lakhs. 2. The applicant / parent should be a permanent resident of Kerala. 3. The child should be certified by a competent authority (under the scheme) regarding need for cochlear implantation surgery. There should not be any medical contraindications to surgery and or

implantation. 4. The parents of the child should be prepared to undergo a mandatory training on speech therapy and post operative care.

Surgical Techniques Classic:

The classic surgery involves Mastoidectomy, posterior tympanotomy, cochleostomy, and insertion of an array of electrodes through the basal turn of the cochlea. The body of the implant is inserted into a seat drilled in the skull in the post aural area. Minimal access surgery for cochlear implantation has been developed in recent years in order to decrease the surgical trauma and secondary complications.

But still, so many patients suffer from complications even now, major ones like meningitis, flap necrosis, device failure, electrode extrusion, facial nerve paralysis and others; while the minor complications involve facial nerve stimulation, electrode migration, vertigo, tinnitus, etc. The major surgical complications which require surgery review and, especially those associated with device insertion are not uncommon. It is well known that there is significant danger of facial nerve and chorda tympani nerve injury in classic approach.

Suprameatal Approach:

The suprameatal approach (SMA) for cochlear implantation is based on retroauricular tympanotomy and does not include Mastoidectomy [10,11]. It eliminates the possible injury to the facial nerve and chorda tympani, shortens the operative time and enables easier drilling of cochleostomy and better control of the electrode insertion. Moreover, it permits the preservation of residual hearing and improves the aesthetic results [12,13]. Thus, SMA is a safe, simple, and quick technique that is feasible for cochlear implantation in most cases. But the stretching of electrode array when it enters the scala tympani and a low-lying dura could

present a potential restriction for the SMA technique [14].

Materials

Study design: Prospective cohort study.

Study setting: Department of ENT, Government Medical College, Kozhikode.

Duration of study: One and half year.

Study period: January 2019 to May 2021.

Study subjects: Cochlear implant candidates in Government Medical College, Kozhikode, under the Sruthitharangam program.

Inclusion Criteria: Children with bilateral severe to profound sensorineural hearing loss were included. Children aged less than 5 years were included. Children with Prelingual hearing impairment were included. Children's parents willing to participate in the study were included.

Exclusion Criteria: Children who have undergone Cochlear implantations done from institutes other than Government medical college, Kozhikode were excluded. Children' parents who excluded.

Sample Size: Sample size was calculated based on the previous study using the formula, Sample size (N) = $4SD^2/d^2$; where SD=standard deviation d= Precision of the study. In a study conducted by Kang J to evaluate radiological parameters related to success of round window approach, the SD of angle between EAC and CBT was 5.95. Applying this value into the equation, at a d of $2n=4SD^2/d^2$; $n=4 \times 5.95 \times 5.95 / 4n=35$

Sample size: 35

Period of Follow Up: 6 months

Study Method: Basic data and patient information was collected using a proforma. Radiological evaluation was done in the preoperative period and peroperative findings noted. 6 months follow up was done and audiological findings were noted at 3 months and 6 months after surgery. Data obtained were entered in the MS Excel Spread sheet and analysed using SPSS 20 version Software. Results were expressed as percentage and frequency. Independent sample t-test /Pearson correlation analysis were performed to find relationship between outcome and various parameters. Paired sample t-test was performed to find the difference in aided audiogram after surgery. Fischer's exact test was performed to find the relationship between round window rotation and various parameters and comparison between surgery findings and CT findings. A p value less than 0.05 was taken as statistically significant.

Results

There were total 40 patients who underwent CI surgery in this study. Initially their demographic data distribution was studied. In this study, almost 27.5% of the cases belong to the age group <3 years and 57.5% of the cases belong to the group 3 years. Around 15.0% cases with age more than 3 years were also noted. The average age was 2.825 years with standard deviation 0.844. The minimum and maximum age was 1 and 5 years respectively. (Table 1) The distribution of gender was observed in this study and found that among 40 cases taken for the study, around 70.0% of the cases were male and 30.0% of the cases were female. The average age of male cases was 2.893 years with standard deviation 0.916. The average age of female cases was 2.667 years with standard deviation 0.651. (Table 1).

Table 1: Shows the Age Gender distribution in the study (n-40).

Observation	Frequency	Percent
Age in Years		
< 03	11	27.5%
03	23	57.5%
>03	06	15.0%
Gender		
Male	28	70.0%
Female	12	30.0%

The mean values of hearing levels obtained in different age groups were compared at 3 months and 6 months post operatively. Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and age is not significant.

That is, age is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is almost same in all three age groups. (Table 2)

Table 2: Showing the Relationship between Outcome and Age at Implantation (n-40).

Age (Years)	Mean	SD	p – value
03 Months			
< 03	43.00	7.071	0.098
03	45.83	7.234	
> 03	38.67	7.501	
06 Months			
< 03	37.73	5.497	0.702
03	38.87	7.194	
> 03	36.50	4.930	

The mean hearing levels obtained after implantation for different age groups at which hearing loss was identified were compared. Here both the p- values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and hearing loss identified is not significant. That is, hearing loss identified is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is almost same in all three groups. (Table 3)

Table 3: Showing the Relationship between Outcome and age at which Hearing Loss was identified (n-40).

Hearing Loss Identified at(Years)	Mean	SD	p – value
3 Months			
Birth	45.50	7.937	0.355
< 01	45.75	7.523	
> 01	42.25	7.376	
06 Months			
Birth	36.25	7.632	0.550
< 01	39.50	6.928	
> 01	37.55	5.835	

The mean hearing levels obtained for two groups were compared, the first group started using hearing aid before one year and the second group after first year of life. Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and hearing aid use

is not significant. That is, hearing aid use is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is almost same in both groups. (Table 4)

Table 4: Shows the Relationship between Outcome and Hearing Aid Use (n-40)

Hearing Aid Use (Years)	Mean	SD	p – value
3 Months			
< 01	44.55	5.820	0.771
> 01	43.76	8.123	
6 Months			
< 01	38.82	5.930	0.711
> 01	37.97	6.641	

The mastoid cellularity obtained from radiological evaluation was compared with surgical findings. Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the CT findings are significantly matching with surgery findings. The table reveals that the CT finding correctly predicting 100.0% sclerotic cases, 80.6% diploic cases and 50.0% pneumatic cases. The accuracy indicates that CT correctly predicting 80.0% cases compared with surgery findings. (Table 5)

Table 5: Shows the Comparison of Mastoid Cellularity between CT and Surgery Findings (n-40)

CT Finding	Surgery Finding			Total	Accuracy	p - value
	Sclerotic	Diploic	Pneumatic			
Hypopneumatized	05(100%)	0 (0.0%)	0 (0.0%)	05	80.0%	0.001
Adequately Pneumatized	03(9.7%)	25(80.6%)	03 (9.7%)	31		
Well Pneumatized	0(0.0%)	02(50%)	02 (50%)	04		
Total	08(20.0%)	27(67.5%)	05 (12.5%)	40		

Figure 1: Figure showing well Pneumatized mastoids

Presence of Korner’s septum was assessed using CT and then compared with surgical findings. Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the CT findings are significantly matching

with surgery findings. The table reveals that the CT finding correctly predicting 100.0% absent cases and 100.0% present cases. The accuracy indicates that CT correctly predicting 100.0% cases compared with surgery findings. (Table 6)

Table 6: Comparison of Korner's septum between CT and surgery findings (n-40)

CT Finding	Surgery Finding		Total	Accuracy	p - value
	Absent	Present			
Absent	36 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	36	100.0%	0.001
Present	0 (0.0%)	04 (100.0%)	04		
Total	36 (90.0%)	04 (10.0%)	40		

The mean values of aided audiograms obtained at 3 months and 6 months postoperatively were compared with the thickness of cochlear nerve. Here both the p- values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and cochlear nerve thickness is not significant. That is, cochlear nerve thickness is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. Non-significant correlation indicates that aided audiogram is not changing with change in cochlear nerve thickness. (Table 7)

Table 7: Relationship between outcome and cochlear nerve thickness (n-40)

Variables	Mean	SD	p - value
Cochlear Nerve Thickness	0.753	0.215	
Aided Audiogram - 3 Months	43.98	7.495	0.295
Aided Audiogram - 6 Months	38.20	6.390	0.318

Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and length of cochlear duct is not significant. That is, length of cochlear duct is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. Non-significant correlation indicates that aided audiogram is not changing with change in length of cochlear duct. (Table 8)

Table 8: Shows the Relationship between hearing outcome and Length of Cochlear Duct (n-40)

Variables	Mean	SD	p - value
Length of Cochlear Duct	28.08	2.377	
Aided Audiogram - 03 Months	43.98	7.495	0.852
Aided Audiogram - 06 Months	38.20	6.390	0.248

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between 'angle between EAC and CBT' and round window rotation is significant. That is, there is significant relationship between 'angle between EAC and CBT' and round window rotation. The table reveals that round window rotation is significantly higher in converging cases (88.9%) compared to diverging (17.2%) and parallel (50.0%). (Table 9)

Table 9: Showing the Relationship between 'Angle between EAC and Cochlear basal turn' and Round Window Rotation (n-40)

Angle between EAC and CBT	Round Window Rotation		Total	p - value
	Yes	No		
Converging	08 (88.9%)	01 (11.1%)	09	0.001
Diverging	05 (17.2%)	24 (82.8%)	29	
Parallel	01 (50.0%)	01 (50.0%)	02	
Total	14 (35.0%)	26 (65.0%)	40	

Figure 2: Showing a diverging angle between Cochlear basal turn and posterior canal wall

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between relative position of IMJ to CBT and round window rotation is significant. That is, there is significant relationship between relative position of IMJ to CBT and round window rotation. The table reveals that round window rotation is significantly higher in cases with relative position in same plane (100.0%) compared to the cases with relative position not in same plane (29.7%). (Table 10)

Table 10: Shows the Relationship between Relative Position of IMJ to Cochlear basal turn and Round Window Rotation (n-40)

Relative Position of IMJ to CBT	Round Window Rotation		Total	p - value
	Yes	No		
Not in same Plane	11 (29.7%)	26 (70.3%)	37	0.037
In same Plane	03 (100.0%)	0 (0.0%)	03	
Total	14 (35.0%)	26 (65.0%)	40	

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between lines along the anterior margin of IAC and round window rotation is significant. That is, there is significant relationship between lines along the anterior margin of IAC and round window rotation. The table reveals that round window rotation is significantly higher in intersect (76.5%) compared to parallel (4.3%). (Table 11)

Table 11: Shows the Relationship between Lines along the Anterior Margins of IAC and Round Window Rotation (n-40)

Lines along the Anterior Margin of IAC	Round Window Rotation		Total	p - value
	Yes	No		
Intersect	13 (76.5%)	04 (23.5%)	17	0.001
Parallel	01 (4.3%)	22 (95.7%)	23	
Total	14 (35.0%)	26 (65.0%)	40	

Figure 3: showing lines drawn along the anterior margin of IACs being parallel

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the CT findings are significantly matching with surgery findings. The table reveals that the CT finding correctly predicting 89.2% normal cases and 100.0% high cases. The accuracy indicates that CT correctly predicting 90.0% cases compared with surgery findings. (Table 12)

Table 12: comparison of Jugular bulb between CT and surgery findings (n-40)

CT Finding	Surgery Finding		Total	Accuracy	p - value
	Normal	High			
Normal	33 (89.2%)	04 (10.8%)	37	90.0%	0.004
High	0 (0.0%)	03 (100.0%)	03		
Total	33 (82.5%)	07 (17.5%)	40		

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the CT findings are significantly matching with surgery findings. The table reveals that the CT finding correctly predicting 94.9% normal cases and 100.0% ante posed cases. The accuracy indicates that CT correctly predicting 95.0% cases compared with surgery findings. (Table 13)

Table 13: Shows the Comparison of Sigmoid Sinus between CT and Surgery Findings (n-40)

CT Finding	Surgery Finding		Total	Accuracy	p - value
	Normal	Anteposed			
Normal	37 (94.9%)	2 (5.1%)	39	95.0%	0.075
Anteposed	0 (0.0%)	01 (100.0%)	01		
Total	37 (92.5%)	3 (7.5%)	40		

Figure 4: showing normal position of Sigmoid sinus and Jugular bulb

The table reveals that the CT finding correctly predicting 92.5% normal cases. The accuracy indicates that CT correctly predicting 92.5% cases compared with surgery findings. (Table 14)

Table 14: Shows the Comparison of level of tegmen between CT and Surgery Findings (n=40)

CT Finding	Surgery Finding		Total	Accuracy	p - value
	Normal	Low Lying			
Normal	37 (92.5%)	3 (7.5%)	40	92.5%	0.001
Abnormal	0	0	0		
Total	37 (92.5%)	3 (7.5%)	40		

Figure 5: showing normal position of tegmen plate, lying at the same level of attic roof

The mean value of audiograms of cases with post meningitis ossification was compared with that of cases with normal cochlea. Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and acquired abnormalities is not significant. That is, acquired abnormalities are not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is slightly higher – not significant – in cases with acquired abnormalities compared to the cases with no abnormalities. (Table 15).

Table 15: Shows the Relationship between Outcome and Acquired Abnormalities (n-40).

Acquired Abnormalities	Mean	SD	p – value
3 Months			
Nil	44.59	7.452	0.066
Yes	36.33	1.155	
6 Months			
Nil	38.73	6.190	0.065
Yes	31.67	6.110	

The mean audiogram values of the cases with complete electrode insertion were compared with that of incomplete insertion. Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and electrode insertion is not significant. That is, electrode insertion is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is almost same in both complete and incomplete. (Table 16)

Table 16: Shows the Relationship between Outcome and Electrode Insertion (n-40)

Electrode Insertion	Mean	SD	p – value
3 Months			
Complete	43.97	7.729	0.994
Incomplete	44.00	5.774	
6 Months			
Complete	38.00	6.659	0.559
Incomplete	40.00	2.944	

The NRTs obtained intraoperatively were compared with the mean hearing level obtained after 3 months and 6 months postoperatively. Here both the p-values are greater than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between outcome and NRTs is not significant. That is, NRTs is not related to outcome at 3 months and 6 months. The table reveals that the aided audiogram is almost same in both groups. (Table 17)

Table 17: Relationship between Outcome and NRT obtained intra-operatively (n-40)

NRT	Mean	SD	p – value
3 Months			
6 – 10	43.80	6.088	0.933
11 – 15	44.03	8.002	
6 Months			
6 - 10	38.50	4.743	0.866
11 - 15	38.10	6.920	

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the relationship between facial nerve thickness and cochlear nerve thickness is significant. That is, there is a significant relationship between facial nerve thickness and cochlear nerve thickness. A significant and positive correlation indicates that cochlear nerve thickness is increasing with increase in facial nerve thickness and decreasing with decrease in facial nerve thickness. (Table 18)

Table 18: Shows the Relationship between Facial Nerve Thickness and Cochlear Nerve Thickness in IAC (n=40)

Variables	Mean	SD	p – value
Facial Nerve Thickness	0.670	0.109	0.014
Cochlear Nerve Thickness	0.753	0.215	

Here the p-value is less than the significance level 0.05; the difference in aided audiogram after surgery is significant. That is, there is a significant difference in aided audiogram after surgery. The table reveals that aided audiogram is significantly reduced after 3 months (43.98 ± 7.495) and further reduced after 6 months (38.20 ± 6.390) compared to the aided audiogram before surgery (77.70 ± 10.82). (Table 19, Fig 6)

Table 19: Shows the Difference in Aided Audiogram after Surgery (n=40)

Aided Audiogram	Mean	SD	p – value
Before Surgery	77.70	10.82	
After 3 Months	43.98	7.495	0.000
After 6 Months	38.20	6.390	0.001

Figure 6: showing the Difference in Aided Audiogram after Surgery

Discussion

Cochlear implantation has radically changed the outlook for profoundly deaf adults and children. The cochlear implant can provide sufficient hearing sensations to enable most severely or profoundly deaf persons to continue communicating using speech as their primary means of communication. In Classic cochlear

implantation Mastoidectomy, posterior tympanotomy and cochleostomy is done. Arrays of electrodes are inserted through the basal turn of the cochlea. But this method is known for complications like facial nerve injury, electrode extrusion etc. The suprameatal approach is based on retroauricular tympanotomy and hence it

eliminates the possibility of facial nerve injury and shortens the operative time, but the stretching of electrode array when it enters the scala tympani, and *low-lying* dura could present a potential restriction for this method. Veria technique is a non-Mastoidectomy technique which is done through the endaural route for the cochleostomy, with a transcanal tunnel drilled in the posterior canal wall. It is thus a minimally invasive method which is more effective and less complicated. The endomeatal approach is another natural access pathway for cochlear implant positioning, with a less traumatic electrode insertion. The benefit of round window approach for cochlear implant is that it represents a natural door to scala tympani, thus allowing for the atraumatic insertion. When the round window anatomy is favourable, direct insertion through the round window membrane is found to be the least traumatic approach. While comparing the initial and delayed intracochlear changes following various methods [15], it was found that the least impact on residual hearing was to be with round window approach. In response to the increased desire in preserving residual hearing, much focus is being given in the selection of surgical technique. Round window insertion is the most accepted surgical approach nowadays, owing to its atraumatic behaviour and lower rates of electrode extrusion, leading to better audiological outcomes. But this method is also not free from limitations. Identification and safe exposure of RW membrane is the pre-requisite for successful electrode insertion, and this highlights the importance of getting a clear idea of the surgical anatomy prior to the surgery. A successful surgical solution for cases involving difficult RW access is well described in literature. So, getting a clear picture of round window anatomy prior to surgery is of utmost importance in making

the surgery most successful and that is what we aimed at in this study. Imaging provides information about the potential difficulties the surgeon may face during the surgery. High-resolution Computed Tomography of the temporal bone and MRI brain are the two most important imaging modalities that may accurately point out the surgical landmarks, anatomical variations, abnormalities and possible difficulties. They both have role in the preoperative assessment of inner ear anomalies, cochlear nerve deficiency, cochlear malformations and syndromes which have prognosticative impact as well. The presence of labyrinthitis ossificans in children with deafness post meningitis may even have a role in the device selection. A proper understanding of the possible anatomical changes of the cochlea is required for avoiding surgical injury causing loss of residual hearing. It can direct a surgeon's way of dealing towards cochleostomy and ultimately introducing the electrode array into scala tympani of basal turn of cochlea to minimize the trauma and thereby preserving remnant neural population and hair cells. In this study we have tried to extract maximum possible information from the available imaging modalities, to find out their implications in round window approach and to correlate them with the surgical findings. We also have tried to compare the audiological outcome at 3 and 6 months postoperatively with the preoperative ones to assess the outcome of surgery, and to find out the effect of early detection and intervention on the final outcome. As a part of the routine workup for cochlear implantation, we already have the High-Resolution Computed Tomography, Magnetic resonance imaging, Aided Audiogram, ASSR, BERA / Audiogram, OAE, Immittance Evaluation, and Speech Language Test available for every patient. So, we conducted the study by making use of these investigation findings

and then comparing them with the intra operative findings and postoperative outcomes. Gathering information starts from the very first visit of the patient to department, enquiring about the antenatal, birth and the postnatal history. Then we followed them up during further visits for audiological evaluation and imaging. The age at which hearing loss was identified and hearing aid use began was enquired and any benefit from using the hearing aid was taken into consideration. The HRCT findings including the Mastoidcellularity, presence of Korner's septum, width of facial recess, descending portion of facial canal, length of cochlear duct, angle between External auditory canal and Cochlear basal turn, Relative position of Incudo-malleal joint and Cochlear basal turn, lines drawn along the anterior margins of Internal acoustic canal, position of Jugular bulb, Sinus plate and tegmen plate, and acquired abnormalities of temporal bone like ossification following meningitis and MRI findings including the thickness of facial nerve and cochlear nerve and the presence of any congenital inner ear anomalies were considered. These were then compared with the intra operative findings like the cellularity of mastoid, presence of Korner's septum, difficult electrode insertion due to narrow facial recess, presence of posteriorly placed round window, position of Jugular bulb, Sigmoid sinus and tegmen plate, and presence of any inner ear anomalies or acquired abnormalities. The intra operative Impedance and NRTs were measured and compared with the audiological assessments at 3 months and 6 months postoperatively. Patient was observed postoperatively for any complications and tried to find out if it was associated with a poorer outcome. The present study questioned whether there was evidence of a benefit to hearing from efforts at providing CIs during early infancy. In a study

conducted by Bruce *et al*, it was found that early implantation can benefit long-term development in two ways [16]. First, it can shorten the interval of deafness with its associated poorer rate of language development, thus reducing the degree to which a child has fallen behind normal-hearing peers at the time of implantation. The data obtained in the study suggested that delays in implantation might have resulted in an ever-increasing gap between the implant candidates and their normal-hearing peers [17,18]. However, in this study we couldn't obtain any significant difference in the audiological outcome of those children implanted at 3 years, below and above 3 years. In a study conducted in Australia in 2013 by Teresa *et al*. to assess the impact of age of amplification on outcomes of children with hearing loss after allowing for the effects of multiple factors, it was found that the age of switch on of children with cochlear implants had a major role to play [7]. In another study called "Early identification and cochlear implantation: Critical factors for spoken language development", the best outcomes occurred in children who underwent implantation at or before 18 months of age and several of these infants demonstrated age-appropriate spoken language skills and so they concluded that early implantation is desirable [17]. But in this study where we compared the hearing outcomes of children whose hearing loss was detected soon after birth and those whom the detection was done before and after 1 year of age, there was no significant association between early identification and better audiological outcome. In an attempt to find out the relationship between the audiological outcome and hearing aid use, we could not get any significant benefit with use of hearing aid before cochlear implantation. The results revealed that the hearing outcome was almost same in those who

started using hearing aid even before one year of age, and those who were much late in using hearing aids. Also, in our study we could not find any significant association between the hearing outcome and length of cochlear duct or cochlear nerve thickness [19]. In our study we tried to compare the HRCT findings like mastoid cellularity, Korner's septum, position of jugular bulb, sigmoid sinus and tegmen with those obtained intraoperatively and could find that much of the HRCT findings were correlating well with the intraoperative findings. To be precise, HRCT had an 80% accuracy in predicting the true mastoid pneumatization and 90% accuracy in predicting the presence of Korner's septum. Both of them were significant as well. This is in accordance with a study in which the authors found a strong correlation between the radiological assessment and surgical findings in the mastoid air cell complex. Also in this study, HRCT was able to predict the true position of jugular bulb with 90% accuracy, Sigmoid sinus with 95% accuracy and Dura with 92.5% accuracy. This is in line with other authors who found a strong correlation between the radiological assessment and surgical findings in the assessment of the position of tegmen and sigmoid sinus. The sigmoid sinus position is particularly important in the Mastoidectomy surgery because the drilling is performed anterior to it. An anteriorly positioned sigmoid sinus may lead to intra operative complication in the form of profuse bleeding. Also, a laterally placed sigmoid sinus can lead to difficulty in round window accessibility. But during our study we did not encounter any such difficulty in approaching the round window. In imaging, the jugular bulb was considered high if it reaches the level of basal turn of cochlea. While doing posterior tympanotomy for cochlear implantation, the round window niche is approached through the facial

recess, which is bounded medially by the vertical segment of facial canal, laterally by the chorda tympani and superiorly by the fossa incudis. The mastoid segment of facial nerve could be injured in case the facial recess is narrow [20]. We used axial images to calculate the width of the facial recess, even though some authors have recommended the use of oblique sagittal sections for the same. According to our study, there was no difficulty encountered while electrode insertion due to an increased facial nerve thickness or narrow facial recess, probably because we have not included those cases with anomalies.

Also, we did not encounter any cases with congenital anomalies of inner ear, as it was excluded from the Sruthitharangam program. The main objective of this study was to find out the implications of radiological parameters in the round window approach of cochlear implantation. In order to find out the potential predictors of round window rotation from the preoperative imaging findings, we measured the angle between External Auditory canal and Cochlear basal turn [21]. The basal turn was selected as it is an indicator en-route to round window and cochlear orientation. And significant relationship was found between an acute angle and posteriorly placed round window. The round window rotation being significantly higher in the cases where these angles were converging (88.9%) than in those cases where these angles were diverging (17.2%) and parallel (50%). Moreover, the presence of incudomalleal joint and cochlear basal turn in the same plane and intersection between the lines drawn through the anterior margin of internal acoustic canal on both sides were pointing towards a posteriorly rotated round window with significant relation. Similarly, an obtuse angle between cochlear basal turn and External acoustic canal, incudo- malleal joint and basal turn of cochlea being in different planes, and lines

drawn through the anterior margin of IAC on both sides being parallel or diverging, these findings pointed towards a normally placed round window with easy access. In our study, only in 3 cases incudo-malleal joint was lying in the same plane as that of the cochlear basal turn and there was significant round window rotation in all of them. And in all cases where

the lines along the anterior margins of internal acoustic canals were found to be intersecting, we could obtain a significant round window rotation (76.5% cases). Thus, we conclude that radiological evaluation is a very good tool to predict the round window accessibility as supported by many other authors.

Figure 7: Figure showing the (a) diverging angle between tangents drawn to the cochlear basal turn and posterior canal wall, (b) parallel anterior margins of IACs (c) and IM joint not in same plane of Cochlear basal turn

Figure 8: Figure showing round window with no posterior rotation

Conclusion

Cochlear implantation has made a huge leap in the treatment of severe to profound sensory neural hearing loss. From this study we could acknowledge the importance of radiological evaluation preoperatively in order to find out the difficulties that may be faced during surgery, potential complications and also for the assessment of round window accessibility with the help of certain radiological parameters. We could also learn about the various factors that may ultimately influence the outcome of surgery and the ease of electrode insertion by knowing the anatomy with accuracy and precision. Moreover, cochlear orientation if studied preoperatively with help of an HRCT temporal bone can guide the surgeon's approach to cochlear implantation.

Limitations

Our study is not without limitations, as our sample size is not large enough to generalize the conclusions, also subjective variations in surgical expertise not taken into account. Our study did not include those cases with cochlea-vestibular anomalies and age more than 5 years. Hence, we recommend for a similar prospective study with a large number of populations including those with inner ear anomalies and also all age groups.

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